

Exploring Artificial Intelligence Applications for Motivating Learners in English as a Second Language Classroom

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Abstract

This paper explores Artificial Intelligence Applications for Motivating Learners in English as a Second Language Classroom. It explains the significance and justifications for employing AI. This paper reviews literature and gives a scholarly background to the study by reviewing some contributions made by various researchers and institutions on AI Education, particularly AI application for education. The paper discusses components of AI education and AI education in the ESL classroom. It also discusses AI applications for evaluation processes and the application of AI from four aspects of English: listening, speaking, writing and translation, and discusses its role in promoting the reform of English teaching. The major conclusion of the study is that the teacher needs to choose the most effective AI application for language learning based on each user's requirements and time constraints in order to motivate the learners accurately. The paper then recommends that English teachers should attempt to explore the possibilities of using AI applications in the English as a second Language classroom in Nigeria to increase the productivity of the class and reduce the amount of responsibilities of the ESL teacher.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Application, Motivation, Second Language, Classroom.*

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Introduction

The digital age and its emergent technologies, including the most recent advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and big data processing, have had unprecedented effects on educational processes and pedagogy, including strategies and approaches related to teaching and acquiring a second language. Graduates of today are members of 'Generation Z', who are known for their digital literacy, technological expertise, and upbringing with digital tools (Al-Qaissi, 2010). In addition, they will shortly be followed by Generation Alpha, whose members are permanently connected and

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capable of making independent decisions. Based on the use of technology and the ability to manage digital identities or visuals, thus, modern second language education is typically technology-based, or it should be, given that technology has become an integral part of the lives of the current generation, as well as the fact that today's language learning environment is no longer limited to the traditional or formal school learning environment (Adilbayeva, Mussanova, Mombekova & Suttibayev, 2022). In this regard, teachers of second languages confront a formidable challenge in integrating various forms of technology into their classrooms in order to meet the needs of their students. To keep up with their digitally savvy students and engage them in learning a second language, however, they must utilize modern technologies such as chatbots and virtual reality (Abdelrady, & Akram, 2022). They must also determine which of these technologies could have an impact in their classrooms, assess their potential, and take advantage of all the benefits they offer. In addition, they should evaluate the potential hazards posed by these technologies. In addition, teachers must always consider the added value of the selected tools for the students' learning and their learning outcomes. This is not a simple task, as research into the practical applications of digital technologies with defined pedagogical goals has not yet produced conclusive results (Woolf, 2022). Results are surprisingly scarce. It should not be forgotten that, as the research emphasizes, instructors of second languages should promote not only their students' acquisition of knowledge (Adilbayeva, Mussanova, Mombekova & Suttibayev, 2022).

However, they should also strengthen the skills that appear to be essential for the 21st century, such as critical thinking, creativity, communication, and collaboration. In addition, teachers must have a positive attitude toward the use of these technologies in Second Language (SL) classrooms and possess the pertinent subject, technological, and pedagogical knowledge in order to motivate students to use these technologies for SL learning (Alemi, Meghdari, & Ghazisaedy, 2015). In the new era, artificial intelligence technology has made an important breakthrough in the field of education and teaching. At present, the accuracy of artificial intelligence speech recognition technology, which is in the leading position in the world, has reached a very high level (Abdelrady, & Akram, 2022). This speech recognition technology is widely used in all aspects of our life. In addition, language translation, speech synthesis, speech testing, speech conversion, voiceprint recognition and other artificial intelligence technologies are also closely related to language learning (Adilbayeva, Mussanova, Mombekova & Suttibayev, 2022). In modern society, machines can not only understand people's words, but also give full feedback to people's words. Artificial intelligence has brought new ideas and breakthroughs to human learning methods, but also challenges and opportunities to all aspects of teaching (Alemi, Meghdari, & Ghazisaedy, 2015).

Artificial is the intelligence shown by machines, whereas Natural Intelligence (NI) displayed by humans and other animals. Any device that perceives its environment and takes actions that maximize its chance of successfully achieving its goals is attributed to have Artificial Intelligence (AI). As a whole, if a machine can initiate the cognitive functions of a human mind such as learning, communicating and problem solving, it is known as Artificial Intelligence (Alemi, Meghdari, & Ghazisaedy, 2015). The specialized areas of AI differ according to requirements. Natural Language processing skills of AI is significant in machine translation and communication, meanwhile, object recognition is important when developing automated vehicles, and similarly, problem-solving skills are essential when developing applications. Thus, different areas of AI can be developed to cater to various aspects of human life. Recent developments have focused on using AI in education to simplify classroom management and increase the

productivity of teaching (Abdelrady & Akram, 2022). As time passes on, machines are becoming more and more complex, fast-processing and intelligent. Being exactly like humans deducting, inferring and making decisions is still away, however, some remarkable gains in the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques and machine learning have been recently recorded. As far as the Nigeria scenario in English as second language classroom is concerned, a typical class contains more than twenty students who are in different proficiency levels. The teacher is required to cater for all language needs of the students while keeping constant records on their development, drawbacks and attendance (Abdelrady & Akram, 2022).

The Significance and Justifications for Employing AI

Employing AI applications for education is a current trend in the field of experimental research (Ge, Yin & Feng, 2018). Studies refer to the diversification of AI education applications, which include programmed learning and other open source high technology. The importance of AI applications in education is determined by their ability to suit the needs and abilities of the learners, to work according to their educational preferences, and to monitor the progress rate of each learner (Ghazi, 2015). These applications contain tracks that suit all learners despite differences among their levels, boost their learning motivation, and cope with students' low levels of attention. They provide feedback that indicates student achievement levels and points of weakness and strength in the scientific content. They ensure that the curriculum subjects are integrated, that the parts of each subject follow logically, and that the learner has mastered one section before moving on to a more advanced one. The scientific content can be introduced in the form of problems, which the students work out according to their self-study streams (Ghazi, 2015). Instructors monitor this process and provide guidance and feedback. AI tutoring systems can replace instructors as they have programmes that provide guidance automatically and enable learners to use self-study skills. AI moves education from a traditional form to an automated education or education through smart interactive machines. It employs natural language to produce new knowledge, and to boost supplementary educational tasks. AI applications can individualize tutoring and introduce varied educational models and streams in which languages are merged with fields of related knowledge (Ge, Yin & Feng, 2018).

Thus, they offer students the chance to learn according to flexible streams that suit their different abilities and academic levels. AI and teaching English as a Second Language require training in and practicing language skills. Since the opportunity to practice these skills in real life situations are often not available, students' chances of mastering these skills are diminished. Therefore, it is necessary to switch from traditional strategies to communicative ones, and rely on digital tools to face difficulties in teaching/learning English (Ge, Yin & Feng, 2018). Teaching English as a second language is regarded as an essential in modern life. The main aim of teaching English is to develop communicative competence, which is achieved through knowing how to use language elements and vocabulary to develop the skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. It also includes how to use language to produce texts, and how to use it to understand reading passages (Abdelrady, & Akram, 2022). The process of language development is based on communication as a goal and as a process. Therefore, using both traditional and digital communication strategies in the teaching/learning processes and activities is necessary. Thus, it is necessary to use AI applications such as simulation and communication programmes as these simulate real

life situations for conversation and communication in English, introduce practical training in language skills, and educational games based on language. Communication tools based on AI help design situations for practicing the accurate pronunciation of letters and words through sound drills and visual media (Abdelrady, & Akram, 2022). Such tools provide exercises for describing and interpreting images and everyday situations, for listening, and for practicing guided pronunciation. They also allow learners to practice language skills and provide feedback for guidance. Some programmes have language drills that give training in communication through using language skills to guarantee that learners reach proficiency levels.

AI can be used to overcome many of the difficulties of teaching/learning English such as prescribes by Al-Qaissi (2010):

- a. using Information Retrieval techniques to build the ability to comprehend reading passages;
- b. employing Machine Translation to develop students' translation skills;
- c. using Automatic Speech Recognition techniques to learn correct pronunciation;
- d. using Text-to-Speech techniques for blind and visually impaired students;
- e. using open digital language dictionaries to enrich the student's vocabulary;
- f. using intelligent programmes to augment speaking skills for English learners;
- g. employing a writing evaluation technique to teach paragraph and essay writing.

Artificial Intelligence Education (AIED)

In 1950s, Alan Turing proposed a solution to the question of when a system designed by a human is 'intelligent.' Turing proposed the imitation game, a test that involves the capacity of a human listener to make the distinction of a conversation with a machine or another human; if this distinction is not detected, it is regarded as an intelligent system, or artificial intelligence (Stefan & Sharon, 2017). When the contemporary situation of education is concerned, AI has already been playing a significant role in the administrative section of several world-renowned universities. For example, universities already use an incipient form of artificial intelligence, IBM's supercomputer Watson. This solution provides student advice for Deakin University in Australia at any time of day throughout 365 days of the year. Even if it is based on algorithms suitable to fulfill repetitive and relatively predictable tasks, Watson's use is an example of the future impact of AI on the administrative workforce profile in higher education (Stefan & Sharon, 2017).

However, Stefan and Sharon (2017) argues that it is important to admit the current limits of technology and admit that AI is not yet ready to replace teachers, but is presenting the real possibility to augment them. They argue that when the real potential of AI is properly used, it would be able to extend human capabilities and possibilities of teaching, learning, and research. In the similar manner, Underwood (2017) proposes that the field of AIED is now mature enough to break away from being delivered mainly through computers and pads so that it can engage with students in new ways and help teachers to teach more effectively (Michael, 2016). Michael brings forth the notion of an 'Educational Cobot', a robot designed to support human teachers. He further discusses that having educational cobots in the classroom would aid the teacher to differentiate instruction so that learners receive more tailored

teaching (Michael, 2016). Underwood and Luckin (2011) discuss the necessity of using AI in education and they state that a key motivation for using AI techniques in the development of Technology Enhanced Learning is to support the development of systems that help teachers and learners to do the right things to maximize learning. This involves understanding and modeling learners, teachers, effective pedagogies and learners' contexts. AIED systems are adaptive, offering support dynamically by responding appropriately to changing and incomplete information about learning objectives, learners, collaborators and context (Underwood & Luckin, 2011).

They elaborate on a current AI system being functioned in Carnegie Learning where they use AI techniques to provide learners of Mathematics with individualized attention and tailored material based on continual assessments. These Cognitive Tutors aim to act like human tutors constantly monitoring learner actions and guiding learners towards correct solutions, providing help on demand and in response to common mistakes and giving meaningful feedback to students on their acquisition of skills (Underwood & Luckin, 2011). Moreover, they elaborate that through Personalisation of the system, it allows learners to work at their own pace, receive targeted feedback, and be supported in their learning without relying on teacher presence. Further, having a flexible learning experience with the support of AI is a way of improving the use of both learner and teacher time, and face-to-face teaching can be replaced by online teaching; individual learning and group work (Underwood & Luckin, 2011).

In the study of Kessler (2018), he argues that Modern learning management systems, along with social media sites, provide a window into such activity in a way that has allowed teachers to understand students' abilities and challenges better. He states that this knowledge can be used to design individualized instruction that caters to specific student needs, including increased uptake of feedback and awareness of linguistic forms. Along with the intervention of increasingly intelligent tools, this type of gathered data can be used to create customized, on-demand feedback and guidance that will address issues related to accuracy in language production as well opportunities to expand fluency and that can be disseminated at the points in the learning process where they are most salient to the learner. Therefore, he concludes that the data gathered through artificial intelligence can thus provide learners with individualized and appropriate support (Kessler, 2018).

AI Applications for Education

The main objectives of AI relate to simulating specific human processes and activities such as learning, thinking, and processing natural language through the technology of knowledge representation. AI applications vary, and that smart systems of online electronic learning are among the most important smart educational systems (Al-Qaissi, 2010). These are the most significant applications of AI use in education. According to Kessler (2018) they are the outcome of merging many systems and applications in the field of AI such as:

- a. Intelligent Tutoring Systems
- b. Activating the Internet
- c. Activating hypermedia
- d. Activating distance E-education

These applications form an integrated network that can develop and update the education process at the levels of inputs, processes, and outputs. AI applications are characterized by interaction between learners and open sources and tools. They also merge real life and virtual reality in an attractive educational milieu and make it possible to use virtual laboratories. According to Woolf (2022) AI education applications are determined according to the following items:

1. natural language processing programmes: are associated with other programmes and systems that can comprehend and generate language. The student interacts with the computer in natural language and the computer understands it;
2. machine programming: The student uses the computer to make software automatically in order to interpret or translate input data;
3. computerized man or robots: The robots can be used to carry out supplementary educational tasks in the school;
4. the computer's ability to see through photo sensors. The computer can analyze pictures and drawings to recognize people and shapes;
5. computer games: include competitive games that a learner can play against the computer. • Expert systems: enable students to build databases in specific fields, which can be used to resolve problems and analyze real life situations;
6. Computer-based Learning: Computers are used in the management of teaching/learning processes, giving instructions to students, and storing and retrieving educational experiences. All of this is implemented in a smart self-study environment.

Components of Artificial Intelligence Education

Computer-Based Training (CBT) and Computer-Aided Instruction (CAI) were the first such systems deployed as an attempt to teach using computers. In these kinds of systems, the instruction was not individualized to the learner's needs and the learner's abilities were not taken into account (Beck, Stern, & Haugsjaa, 2015). While both CBT and CAI may be somewhat effective in helping learners, they do not provide the same kind of individualized attention that a student would receive from a human tutor (Underwood, 2017).

For a computer based educational system to provide such attention, it must reason about the domain and the learner. This has prompted research in the field of Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITSs). ITSs offer considerable flexibility in presentation of material and a greater ability to respond to idiosyncratic student needs. These systems achieve their 'intelligence' by representing pedagogical decisions about how to teach as well as information about the learner. This allows for greater versatility by altering the system's interactions with the student. Woolf (2022) has identified four major components in Artificial Intelligence education as: the student model, the pedagogical module, the domain knowledge module, and the communication module and in addition, Beck, Stern, and Haugsjaa, (2015) have identified a fifth component as the expert model. According to Michael (2016) the functions of these five models can be simply elaborated as follows.

1. Student Model: stores information on every learner in a class such as attendance, assignment marks etc.

2. **Pedagogical Module:** provides a model of the teaching process, such as student review dates, suitable moment to give the students a new topic to write, and the best topic for a writing activity etc. More importantly, this model can communicate with the student module and assess the proficiency level of every student to choose the best teaching process to assure the quality of the class.

3. **Knowledge Domain:** stores all the information, in ESL situation, grammar, vocabulary, reading comprehension skills and listening skills and all the lessons and activities the teacher has prepared to do in the class. This is considered as the most important component as, without it, there would be nothing to teach the student.

4. **Communications Module:** carries out interactions with the learners in the class including verbal communication, email handling and the screen layouts.

5. **Expert Model:** similar to the domain knowledge, since it must contain the information being taught to the learner. However, it is more than just a representation of the data; it is a model of how someone skilled in a particular domain represents the knowledge and is capable of solving problems in the domain, and this model can compare its solution to a problem with the learner's solution and pinpoint the places where the learner has to improve. In ESL context, the expert model can compare its grammar with the learner's grammar and point the areas they should reconsider.

The following diagram shows how these five models interact with each other.

Figure1. Interactions of Components in an Intelligent Tutoring System

Source: Stern., & Haugsjaa, 2015

Artificial Intelligence Education (AIEd) in the ESL Classroom

'Intelligence Unleashed: An argument for AI in Education' offers a comprehensive account on the current use of AIEd in ESL classroom and the future of its horizons. According to Luckin, Holmes, Griffiths and Forcier (2016), the key models at the heart of AIEd: the pedagogical model, the domain model, and the learner model, which have the functions discussed above. In addition to the aforesaid, there are Open Learner Models, which present the outcomes of the analysis back to the learners and teachers. These results tend to carry information about each learner's achievements, their proficiency level, and their development, which are valuable for the teachers to understand each student's approach to learning, and allow them to shape future learning experiences appropriately. At the same time, Open Learner Models can motivate the learners by providing them with the details of their progress in learning.

In addition to these uses, many institutions use AIEd and Educational Data Mining (EDM) techniques to keep track on the student behaviors, i.e. class attendance, assignment submissions and marks to identify and support the students who tend to drop out of the colleges (Luckin, Holmes, Griffiths & Forcier, 2016).

Moreover, 'Intelligence Unleashed: An argument for AI in Education' introduces three categories of AIEd software applications to support teaching and learning process (Luckin, Holmes, Griffiths & Forcier, 2016).

1. Personal tutors for every learner is one-to-one human tutoring, which is the most effective approach to teaching and learning. However, it is considered as impractical as there will not be enough personal tutors for every learner and it would be expensive.

2. Intelligent support for collaborative learning has been suggested to use between a pair of students undertaking a project together and a community of students participating in an online course because it has been proven to have higher learning outcomes than learning alone. On the contrary, several studies argue that group members might not have the social interaction skills needed to collaborate effectively. This can be especially difficult in the context of online collaborations, where participants rarely meet in person.

3. Intelligent virtual reality provides authentic experiences that simulate some aspect of the real world to which the user would not otherwise have access. For instance, a flight stimulator provides a situation a pilot student cannot experience in real life, the student is provided with a real scenario and his responses, and development is tracked during his training.

Thus, the AIEd offers a multi-faceted approach to teach and learning, and several components from these can be used to improve the three core components of learning: curriculum, learning and teaching, and assessment. Underwood (2017) conducted a nine-month research study employing Amazon's Alexa, Apple's Siri, Google voice search, and co-design methods with a class of primary age English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students to explore and develop ideas for classroom activities using AI language assistants. The results revealed that speaking to AI assistants was considered highly engaging by all students, and it was evident that students spoke more English when using AI assistants in group work compared to a teacher environment. Moreover, the spontaneously engaged in self-correction and were enthusiastic to get AI assistants to do what they wanted them to do. This study proved that learning experience can be effortless and joyful when using AI assistants. In addition, Underwood (2017) proves the necessity for incorporating AI in Education by stating drivers for such research include the desire to give individual students more attention in large classes and the observation that children often enjoy talking to robots and are more relaxed using a foreign language to speak with machines than with humans (Underwood, 2017).

Moreover, in the study of Alemi, Meghdari, and Ghazisaedy (2015) which aimed to examine the effect of Robot Assisted Language Learning (RALL) on the anxiety level and attitude in English vocabulary acquisition amongst Iranian EFL junior high school students conducted an experiment with forty-six female students, who were beginners at the age of 12. They were randomly assigned into two groups of as RALL (30 students) and non-RALL (16 students). However, in the RALL group, the treatment was given by a teacher accompanied by a humanoid robot assistant. Two questionnaires of anxiety and attitude were utilized to measure the students' anxiety and attitude. The results indicated that there was lower anxiety and a more positive

attitude towards English vocabulary acquisition in the RALL group compared with those in the non-RALL group. The study showed that the students in the RALL group had great fun in the learning process; they also believed they were learning more effectively, which helped them boost their motivation in the long run. Thus, their study provides new insights into the use of technology in the language classroom, suggesting that teachers and material developers should integrate technology into the language learning process (Alemi, Meghdari & Ghazisaedy, (2015).

AI Applications for Evaluation Processes

The importance of AI applications in analyzing and producing the results of student evaluation processes at the secondary and pre-secondary stages. AI makes it easy for instructors to measure their students' levels precisely, which is something often difficult to achieve. It enables university teaching staff to assess the level of the educational processors and determine deficiencies in the lectures, scientific content, and the educational material introduced to students. AI helps meet the needs of each student according to his/her abilities and needs by introducing home assignments and monitoring the scores obtained by each student because it has smart programmes that identify the students' common mistakes, gives the instructors hints as to what the problems are, and introduces instant feedback in a file designed separately for each student (Underwood, 2017). Furthermore, AI tools and programmes can cope with classroom density. From the information above, it can be concluded that AI focuses on two issues. The first, the theoretical issue, relates to describing and interpreting mental processes and activities and representing human behavior in real tasks and situations (Luckin, Holmes, Griffiths & Forcier, 2016). On the other hand, the second or applied issue is concerned with employing smart tools and machines to represent human behavior. AI includes some applications that can generally be employed to perform educational tasks such as representing and storing knowledge, introducing varied models for student-student and student-machine interaction. AI can enhance the learning process with programmes that translate accurately between English and Arabic according to modern dictionaries, which provide an accurate meaning of the vocabulary items according to their contexts (Beck, Stern, & Haugsjaa., 2015). These programmes can introduce some ideas about the reading passages, arrange words to make sentences and paragraphs, and use sounds to identify letters and words. They can identify word maps and link texts, pictures and sounds together.

The Application of Artificial Intelligence Technology in English Teaching

In the field of language learning, artificial intelligence can play its unique advantages. It plays an important auxiliary role in students' learning and teachers' teaching. The application of artificial intelligence technology in English teaching can give full play to its advantages and make up for the shortcomings of traditional classroom teaching. This paper discusses the application of artificial intelligence from four aspects of English: listening, speaking, writing and translation, and discusses its role in promoting the reform of English teaching.

The Application of Artificial Intelligence Technology in English Listening Teaching

Listening teaching is the beginning of learning a language and occupies a basic position in English teaching. As an indispensable part of students' English learning process, listening training is of great significance to the cultivation of students' Basic English

literacy. However, due to many reasons such as the boring content of listening materials, the difficulty of listening and the inflexibility of teaching methods, students have some fear and resistance to English listening courses (Adilbayeva, Mussanova, Mombekova & Suttibayev, 2022). Corpus based English listening teaching can provide learners with a large amount of listening materials. Different difficulties and themes can meet the real needs of many students for English listening. The application of AI technology to English Listening Teaching Based on corpus can help students to match learning resources automatically. AI technology can automatically match the listening materials suitable for the students from the corpus, improve the students' interest in learning, and reduce the burden of English listening by analyzing the factors such as students' age, English level and major. Second, students can choose the corresponding English learning materials according to their own interests and their own plans for the future career to conduct in-depth and comprehensive learning. Third, it can realize the interaction between learning and situation. For example, when students scan an object around them, AI can automatically recognize and explain the object in English, which realizes the close connection between listening practice and life (Abdelrady, & Akram, 2022).

Application of Artificial Intelligence Technology in English Writing

The application of AI technology in English writing teaching is mainly reflected in the correction of English composition content (Chen, Sha, He & Wang, 2017). Firstly, the teacher arranges the writing task in the composition system. The students can write in the composition system after receiving the homework. The AI system can provide students with an idea and framework for learning and doing, provide corresponding vocabulary reference in the specific writing, and assist students to complete the task. After the completion of the system for review, students can know their level of learning and doing at the first time, and correct the problems in writing. Through this process, we can help students find out and fill in the gaps in time, and strengthen their writing ability. Such as: correction network. This kind of intelligent teaching platform can give timely and effective feedback to students' uploaded English compositions, and make objective evaluation on students' English compositions. The system can make a comprehensive analysis of the students' English composition, make a basic judgment on the structure of the students' articles, correct the spelling errors and many grammatical errors in the articles in time, and put forward the modification suggestions in time. Introduce an automatic online correction service tool into English writing teaching, give full play to its advantages of personalization, instant feedback, comment on sentences, online modification, etc., let students have fun in writing in the process of multi manuscript modification, realize self-exploration and self-innovation construction, enhance their sense of self-efficacy in writing ability, and improve their motivation and writing ability (Chen, Sha, He & Wang, 2017). Teachers can use the system's automatic feedback mechanism to make manual secondary correction and make further teaching feedback. Teachers can also master students' learning situation and implement curriculum improvement at any time according to the formative assessment report given by the system, which is of great significance for improving teaching methods and realizing the upgrading of teaching system.

Application of Artificial Intelligence Technology in English Translation Teaching

Artificial intelligence technology realizes the accuracy and real-time of translation, which is a huge test for students' translation ability. Using cloud platform to realize the translation teaching of AI, the first embodiment is the translation process. The

introduction of AI into translation teaching can create translation situations for students and provide guidance and help for students' translation (Al-Qaissi, 2010). In this process, students can solve a large part of the difficulties and doubts of translation through AI, which to a certain extent will stimulate students to explore the fun of deep learning and enhance their enthusiasm for translation. The second is translation evaluation. Create translation tasks on the cloud platform. The AI system can track each translation of students to form a dynamic evaluation. Teachers can supervise the whole translation process, timely and accurately understand each student's translation characteristics, quantify the translation results of students, and realize the personalized guidance of students AI also has a breakthrough in the field of English translation.

Application of Artificial Intelligence Technology in Spoken English

The ultimate goal of oral English learning is to achieve fluent communication. The level of students' oral English expression can fully demonstrate their practical English application ability. Therefore, according to Chen, Sha, He and Wang (2017) the introduction of AI technology into English teaching has obvious advantages. First, it can realize the accompanying practice. AI robot can create English learning environment for students and communicate with students like partners (Intelligent Learning Institute of Beijing Normal University, 2016). Through human-computer conversation, not only can we avoid the embarrassment in practice, but also can improve our oral English level quickly. Second, teachers and students can practice in groups by remote way to achieve group learning in holidays. Intelligent robot can act as a teaching assistant, providing some sentence patterns and fixed collocations for practice activities, which is convenient for group members to practice. In this process, the tension between students and real people can be fully and effectively relieved to help students practice and improve their oral English fluency. In today's oral English teaching, we should promote the in-depth promotion of robot teaching and realize the full and effective development of oral English teaching. This has a great role in improving students' English ability (Chen, Sha, He & Wang, 2017).

Conclusions

In a word, the application of artificial intelligence in language teaching is still in the primary stage, but it has shown great potential. AI tools will be more useful in adaptive and individualized learning which satisfies the needs of the students. AI helps the teachers to know the understanding capacity of the students on their lectures and enable them to provide the relevant hints for students. It acts as a tutor for the students and helps them to learn. Artificial intelligence driven programmes offer helpful feedback for both students and teachers. It helps the teachers to monitor the performance of the students and enable them improve the instruction that they provide for the students. AI systems in schools have changed the way students find and interact with integrated technology. This has an effect to change teachers as facilitators by providing students interactive learning experience. Students can learn by the trial and error method without fear as AI supports in their learning and provide assistant for their improvement. Artificial intelligence systems acquired-data will change the way the schools find, teach and support students. If goes beyond the reach, it may even replace teachers in certain instance. It has become a learning companion that assists students in their learning process. The role that Artificial intelligence application plays in education is remarkable in this technological world and it is expected to advance learning experience more and more in the near future AI tools

are inherently engaging and intrinsically motivating players to learn and progress accordingly, and increase their self-efficacy, which in turn may increase students' academic achievements. The teacher needs to choose the most effective AI applications for language learning based on each user's requirements and time constraints in order to motivate them accurately. In order to safeguard the application of AI in education it should be lawful, complying with all applicable laws and regulations; it should be ethical, ensuring adherence to ethical principles and values; and it should be robust, both from a technical and social perspective, since, even with good intentions, AI systems can cause unintentional harm.

Recommendations

English language teachers' plan should include the basics, objectives, content, processors, and evaluation methods for the employment of AI applications in the field of English education.

Along the same vein, employing AI applications will help develop language communication skills through intelligent dialog boxes. For Language development processors, language teachers should engage a variety of intelligent sources, windows for dialogs and discussion, intelligent tools for communication, programmes that generate texts for reading, and programmes that extract information from reading passages. Such props will develop reading comprehension skills.

In addition, AI should be employed to develop teaching strategies and evaluation methods by individualizing self-study processes, and simulating through smart and expert systems.

Language teachers should attempts to explore the possibilities of using Artificial intelligence in the English as a second Language classroom in Nigeria to increase the productivity of the class and reduce the amount of responsibilities of the ESL teacher.

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